

Temperature Coefficients of Photochemical Reactions.

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In several publications from these laboratories (Mukherji and Dhar, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1929, **33**, 850; Bhattacharya and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1928, **176**, 372; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **6**, 143; Verma and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1929, **184**, 90; Bhagwat and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, **197**, 23 ; Malaviya and Dhar, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, **199**, 400), it has been shown experimentally that the temperature coefficient of a photochemical reaction is always less than that taking place in the dark. Moreover, it has been observed with numerous photochemical reactions taking place in radiations of different wavelengths that the temperature coefficient of a reaction depends on the acceleration of the reaction on illumination. The greater the acceleration of a reaction in light, the smaller is the value of its temperature coefficient. It has been emphasised in our publications that the influence of temperature, of light and of a positive catalyst on a reaction appears to be identical.

In this communication we shall deduce a relation by which the temperature coefficient of a photochemical reaction can be predicted from the temperature coefficient of the dark reaction and its photochemical acceleration at a definite temperature. Moreover, we shall critically examine certain views expressed in recent years correlating velocity and temperature of a photochemical reaction.

Arrhenius (*Z. phys. Chem.*, 1889, **4**, 226) formulated the following empirical relation for the velocity coefficient of a thermal reaction at two temperatures from considerations based on the existence of active and inactive molecules in a system.

$$K_{t_2} = K_{t_1} e^A$$

Marcelin (*Compt. rend.*, 1913, **157**, 1419; 1914, **158**, 116, 407; *Ann. Physique*, 1915, *ix*, **3**, 120), and Rice (*Brit. Assoc. Rep.*, 1915, p. 827) by applying statistical mechanics arrived at the same conclusion.

The influence of light on a reaction appears to be similar to that of temperature on the same reaction and consists in increasing the

number of active molecules. Hence it is possible to connect the amount of activation or acceleration due to light in terms of temperature effect. Assuming that the intensity of light remains the same when the temperature is varied, the photochemical effect in terms of temperature remains constant. Thus from the knowledge of the dark velocity coefficient and the photochemical acceleration at one temperature, it is possible to calculate the photochemical velocity coefficient at any other temperature. Moreover the thermal temperature coefficient can directly be connected with the photochemical temperature coefficient.

Let K_1 be the dark velocity coefficient at temperature T_1 , and K_2 be the dark velocity coefficient at temperature T_2 where $T_2 - T_1 = 10$.

Let K'_1 be the light velocity coefficient at temperature T_1 (all temperatures are expressed in absolute scale), then

$$K_2 = K_1 e^{A \left(\frac{1}{T_1} - \frac{1}{T_2} \right)} \quad \text{or} \quad A = \frac{T_1 \cdot T_2}{10} \log x, \quad \text{where} \quad x = \frac{K_2}{K_1}$$

$$\text{also} \log \frac{K'_1}{K_1} = \log y = A \left(\frac{T_x - T_1}{T_1 \cdot T_x} \right)$$

where T_x is the temperature of the dark reaction corresponding to the photochemical velocity coefficient K'_1 , then

$$T_x = \frac{T_1 \cdot T_2 \log x}{T_2 \log x - 10 \log y}$$

Hence the photochemical acceleration corresponds to the rise in temperature

$$T_x - T_1 = \frac{10 T_1 \log y}{T_2 \log x - 10 \log y}$$

Therefore the photochemical velocity coefficient at T_2 is equal to the dark velocity coefficient at $T_2 + T_x - T_1$.

$$\text{Thus} \quad K'_2 = K_2 e^{\frac{T_1^2 \log x \cdot \log y}{T_2^2 \log x - 10^2 \log y}}$$

$$\text{and} \quad K'_1 = K_1 c^{\log y}$$

Hence the temperature coefficient of a photochemical reaction

$$= \frac{K'_2 - K_2}{K'_1 - K_1} = \frac{K_2}{K_1} \left(\frac{e^{\log m} - 1}{e^{\log y} - 1} \right) \quad \text{where } \log m = \frac{T_1^2 \log x \log y}{T_2 \log x - 10^2 \log y}$$

where $\frac{K_2}{K_1}$ is the dark temperature coefficient.

The applicability of this relation has been tested by modifying this equation. When the photochemical acceleration is small, $10^2 \log y$ can be neglected compared to $T_1^2 \log x$. Hence $\log m = \frac{T_1^2}{T_2} \log y$. The equation can be written as

$$\frac{K'_2 - K_2}{K'_1 - K_1} = \frac{K_2}{K_1} \left(\frac{e^{\frac{T_1^2}{T_2} \log Ky} - 1}{e^{\log y} - 1} \right)$$

and the value of K can be calculated when we know both the temperature coefficients of the dark and photochemical reactions. If the value of K is unity it is clear that the equation holds good. It has been observed that for small accelerations in case of numerous reactions and for various wavelengths the value of K varies from 0.97 to 1.01. This relation has been found to be applicable to the following photochemical reactions: Sodium malonate and iodine, potassium oxalate and bromine, citric acid and potassium permanganate, bleaching of dicyanin, sodium formate and iodine, chromic acid and oxalic acid, sodium formate and mercuric chloride, sodium potassium tartrate and bromine, quinine sulphate and chromic acid, potassium permanganate and oxalic acid, sodium lactate and iodine, sodium tartrate and iodine and many other reactions. This relation holds good when the photochemical acceleration is small, but appears to be inapplicable in some cases where the photochemical acceleration is very high.

The equation

$$\frac{K'_2 - K_2}{K'_1 - K_1} = \frac{K_2}{K_1} \left(\frac{c \frac{T_1^2 \log x \log y}{T_2 \log x - 10^2 \log y} - 1}{e^{\log y} - 1} \right)$$

shows not only that smaller the photochemical acceleration over the dark reaction, the greater is the photochemical temperature coefficient, but it also shows that it approaches the dark temperature coefficient more and more and in the limit it is equal to it and can never be greater than the dark temperature coefficient.

It follows from the law of photochemical equivalence first enunciated by Einstein that the temperature should have no effect on the velocity of photochemical reactions. In deducing this law, Einstein has made the assumption that all the molecules in a system possess the same amount of energy and are in the same state of activation. It is clear from Maxwell's law of distribution that all molecules can not possess the same amount of energy. Moreover, the kinetic energy of the molecules increases with temperature. It appears, therefore, that Einstein's law of photochemical equivalence cannot explain the observed temperature coefficient of photochemical reactions.

In order to explain the influence of temperature on the velocity of a photochemical reaction, it is generally assumed that molecules which have absorbed a quantum of light of stated frequency are often only activated if they already possess, before absorption, energy greater than a critical limit. If we represent by 'e' the critical increment, that is, the amount of energy which must be given to a molecule to render it chemically active, the thermal acceleration of the reaction taking place in the dark is given by

$$\frac{d \log K}{dT} = \frac{Ne}{RT^2}$$

In order that a molecule can be brought into active state by a quantum of light, its energy must exceed the molecular energy by at least $e - h\nu$. The velocity of the thermal acceleration of the photochemical reaction is thus expressed by the equation

$$\frac{d \log K}{dT} = \frac{N(e - h\nu)}{RT^2}$$

According to this formulæ the thermal acceleration is less for the photochemical reaction than for the same reaction carried in the dark. Tolman (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, **45**, 2285) has come to the conclusion that the temperature coefficient of a photochemical reaction is unity when the average energy of the reacting system is the same as the average energy of the reacting molecules and this

is actually the assumption made by Einstein in deducing his law of photochemical equivalence.

Recently A. Berthoud (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1931, 27, 486) from considerations based on the limiting energies of molecules obtainable by integrating Maxwell's formulæ, has taken objection to the above equation, because it leads to the view that the velocity of a reaction ought to increase very rapidly with the frequency and to become independent of frequency after a limiting value of the frequency. But this is not supported by experimental results. In almost all photochemical reactions, increase of the quantum yield is observed in a very wide spectral zone with increase of frequency.

Bodenstein (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1913, 85, 318) suggested that for the occurrence of a photochemical reaction, it is necessary to have not only the activation of light absorbing component of the reacting system but also an activation of the other reactant is essential. According to Bodenstein this activation should be possible by the energy of the thermal agitation. Hence the photochemical reaction taken as a whole becomes sensitive to changes of temperature. It is clear from the above view of Bodenstein that the temperature coefficient of a thermal reaction should be higher than that of photochemical reaction, because in the thermal reaction the activation of both the reactants is due to the supply of thermal energy.

It is difficult to conceive that out of two types of reacting molecules, one type only will be affected by increase of temperature. It seems more plausible to assume that the amount of energy absorbed by one type of molecules is different from that taken up by the other.

Let us consider a reaction of the type.

Let us assume the amount of light taken up by the two types of molecules to be different and K_a and K_b the energies absorbed where $K_a + K_b = A'$ the total light absorbed by the reacting system. Let the energy due to temperature $T_1 = x + y$ of which x is the amount taken up by A type of molecules and y by B type of molecules. Let z be the energy due to temperature T_2 , then $\frac{zx}{x+y}$ will be taken by A type of molecules and

$\frac{zy}{x+y}$ will be taken by the B type of molecules.

have actually observed that the extinction coefficient increases with temperature. But this can not be the cause of increased quantum yield with temperature. Contrary to the statement of Young and Style, (*loc. cit.*) Bhattacharya and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) have shown that the quantum yield falls with the increased absorption. This will be clear from some of their results given below:—

No.	Source of light.	Reaction mixture.	Temp.	Diameter of the aperture of the iris-diaphragm in cm.	Quantum yield.
1.	1000 watt lamp	20% Cane sugar (15 c.c.) and $\frac{N}{20}$ HCl (5 c.c.)	35°	2	16.5×10^2
	"	"	"	0.8	19.2×10^2
2.	4725 Å	$\frac{N}{101.7}$ Br and 43% methyl alcohol (10 c.c. each)	20°	2	6.2
	"	"	"	0.8	7.9
3.	4725 Å	$\frac{N}{113.7}$ Br and 25% ethyl alcohol (10 c.c. each)	20°	2	3.2
	"	"	"	0.8	4.6
4.	4725 Å	49% Acetone (5 c.c.) $\frac{N}{50}$ iodine	31°	2	41
	"	(10 c.c.) and $\frac{N}{9.42}$ HCl (5 c.c.)	"	0.8	53

Similar decrease of quantum yield with increase of light intensity has been observed with several other photochemical reactions.

The foregoing results show that the quantum yield decreases as the amount of light falling on the reacting mixture is increased. It has been observed that the amount of absorption is directly proportional to the amount of the incident radiation. Hence we can conclude that greater the intensity, the less is the quantum yield. The reason of this decrease in quantum yield with increased absorption of intensity is not far to seek. In a paper (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1931, 199, 406) concerning the relation between light intensity and velocity of photochemical reactions, we have shown that the amount of activation for the same increase of intensity or absorption falls as the intensity or absorption is increased and hence the amount of reaction per unit of absorption or quantum yield falls as the absorption or intensity increases. Thus the conclusion of Young and Style that

increased absorption with rise of temperature is one of the causes of increased quantum yield seems to be incorrect. The fact that the photochemical temperature coefficient is partially governed by the thermal one indicates that the mechanism of the photo-reaction is more or less allied to that of the dark reaction, although the increased light absorption with temperature increases the internal energy and chances of collision and thus the mechanism of the photo-reaction may be modified.

Summary.

The temperature coefficient of a photochemical reaction can be calculated from the temperature coefficient of the dark reaction and its photo-acceleration at a definite temperature.

Tolman's conclusion that the temperature coefficient of a photochemical reaction is unity when the average energy of the system is the same as the average energy of the reacting molecules, is inherent in Einstein's deduction of the photo-equivalence law.

Bodenstein's suggestion that out of two reacting molecules only one type of reacting molecules is activated by absorption of light and the other type by temperature only leads to conclusion unwarranted by experiments.

Increased light absorption with increase of temperature cannot be the cause of the increased quantum yield with increase of temperature. Results obtained in this laboratory show that the increase of light absorption leads to a decrease of the quantum yield and this can be satisfactorily explained from our view point that the number of molecules available for activation by light absorption decreases with increased absorption.